

Adhesive joint strength of glass/epoxy composites surface-treated with nano-size carbon black

Sang Wook Park and Dai Gil Lee*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, ME3221, Guseong-dong, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon 305-701, Republic of Korea, yoll@kaist.ac.kr

SUMMARY

The surface of glass/epoxy composite material was embedded with carbon black diluted in methyl ethyl ketane (MEK) during curing process to enhance the adhesion strength of the glass/epoxy composite structure. The morphological effect of the carbon black on the surface of composite was observed using SEM and AFM. Quantitative chemical bonding analysis with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was also performed to observe chemical binding states on the surface. The lap shear strength of the glass/epoxy adhesive joints whose adherends were embedded with carbon black was investigated with respect to the amount of embedment. Also, the tensile properties of the carbon black embedded glass/epoxy composite were measured to observe the mechanical degradation of the composite due to the MEK. The surface free energies of carbon black embedded composites were calculated from the van Oss-Chaudhury Good equation to correlate the lap shear strength of the adhesive joints with their surface free energies.

Keywords: Adhesive joint, carbon black, particle embedded composite

1 Introduction

The development of reliable joining methods for composite assemblies has become an important research area because large or complex composite structures are usually required to be joined to other metallic or ceramic parts to enhance their performance. The efficiency of composite structures with joints is largely dependent on these joints rather than their structures, because the joint is usually the weakest part among the components of assembled structures [1-3].

Generally, joining methods for composite assemblies are classified into adhesive bonding and mechanical fastening. The adhesive joint distributes the load over a larger area than the mechanical joint, requires no holes, adds very little weight to the structure and has superior fatigue resistance.

In order to get a strong and durable joint between composite assemblies, surface treatment is necessary prior to bonding. Several methods to improve the bonding strength of the composite assemblies have been investigated. Niem et al. [4] studied the joint strength with respect to the surface roughness and surface treatment direction of the adherends. Roizard et al. [5] investigated the alkaline etching treatment of glass/epoxy composite substrate for micro-scale roughness. Kim and Lee [6] studied plasma surface treatment on carbon fiber/epoxy composites to improve the load capabilities of composite adhesive joints.

Although these surface treatments yielded reliable adhesive joints, they increased the preparation time of composite components, emitted fiber dusts and used toxic chemicals. Therefore, some researchers investigated alternative fabrication methods for

composite structure which did not require surface treatment for adhesive joining. Benard et al. [7] studied the peel ply surface treatment and its surface characteristics for composite assemblies, where surface roughness in micro scale was generated on the composite assemblies. Some researchers investigated carbon black reinforced composites to improve wear characteristics and carbon black reinforced adhesives for better adhesion [8,9]. However, there are only a few researches on the surface characteristics of the particle reinforced polymeric composites, specially nano particle reinforced and their relations to the adhesion characteristics.

Therefore, in this work, the surfaces of glass/epoxy composite materials were embedded with nano-size carbon black which was diluted in methyl ethyl ketane (MEK) during curing process to enhance the adhesion characteristics of the glass/epoxy composite structure. In order to observe the surface modification of the composite due to the dilution of resin during curing process by MEK, the surface morphology of the composite was observed with a SEM (scanning electron microscope) and the surface roughness of composite surface was measured with respect to the amount of MEK. Then, the static tensile load capability of the adhesively bonded double lap joint whose adherends were composed of the MEK treated glass/epoxy composite was investigated with respect to the amount of MEK. The mechanical properties of the glass/epoxy composite were measured to investigate the minimum amount of MEK which did not degrade the composite due to the dilution of resin during curing process.

The effect of the embedded carbon black particle on the adhesion strength of the composites was measured using double lap joints with respect to the amount of embedment. The surface morphology of carbon black embedded composite was observed with an AFM (Atomic force microscope) to investigate the enhancement mechanism of adhesion strength due to nano-sizes carbon black particle. Quantitative chemical bonding analysis with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed to observe chemical binding states on the surface. Also, the surface free energies of carbon black embedded composites were calculated using the van Oss-Chaudhury Good equation [10]. Finally, the lap shear strength of the double lap joint whose adherends were embedded with the optimum amount of carbon black particle was compared to those of the double lap joints whose adherends were mechanically abraded or grit-blasted.

2. Experimental

2.1 Fabrication of the carbon black embedded composite

Glass fiber epoxy composite prepregs (UGN150, SK Chemicals, South Korea) were used to fabricate the adherends of the double lap joint. Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of the glass/epoxy composite. Carbon black (EC-300J, Ketjenblack, Japan), nano-clay (Cloisite 93A, S.C.P. Inc., U.S.A.), and SiO₂ (Z406627, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) were embedded in the glass fiber-epoxy composite prepreg. Table 2 shows the properties of the carbon black used.

Fig. 1 shows the fabrication procedure for the carbon black embedded composite. The carbon black particles were diluted in methyl ethyl ketane (MEK) to prevent drifting of the particles in the air during deposition on the surface of composite prepreg. Then, the diluted carbon black was sprayed on the stacked glass/epoxy prepregs, followed by drying the prepregs at 25° C for 1 hour to eliminate the MEK as shown in Fig. 1 (b). The carbon black deposited prepregs were cured at 125° C for 2.5 hours

using vacuum bag degassing process. The surfaces of the cured composite were observed with the SEM (XL30SFEG, Philips, The Netherlands) and the arithmetic surface roughness was measured with the surface roughness tester (NT57-042, Mitutoyo, Japan).

2.2 Tensile test of the composite adherend

The tensile test specimens of glass/epoxy composite shown in Fig. 2 were fabricated according to ASTM D3039 with respect to the sprayed amount of MEK during the curing process. The tensile tests were performed with the material testing machine (Instron 4408, MA, U.S.A.). The displacement rate of the tensile test was set to be 1.0 mm/min.

2.3 Tensile test of the adhesively bonded joints

The adhesively bonded double lap joints whose adherends were composed of the carbon black embedded glass/epoxy composite were fabricated as shown in Fig. 3. The thickness of the epoxy adhesive layer was fixed to be 0.1 mm for the maximum joint strength [11]. Table 3 shows the mechanical properties of an epoxy adhesive (XB5013, Huntsman, U.S.A.) used in the study. The adhesively bonded joint was cured at 25°C for 24 hours, followed by the post-cure at 80°C for 2 hours. After curing the adhesively bonded joint, the adhesive fillets of the joint were removed with a razor blade to eliminate the effect of the fillet. The right side bonding length of the joint was 20 mm, while the left side bonding length was 30 mm to make the joint fail at the right side as shown in Fig. 3 (a). The width of the joint was fixed to be 20 mm. The tensile load capability of the joints was measured with respect to the amount of MEK on the prepreg, the amount of embedded particle on the composite adherend with the material testing machine (Instron 4408, MA, U.S.A.). The displacement rate of the tensile test was set to be 1.0 mm/min. From the measured static tensile load capability F , the average static lap shear strength τ was calculated as follows.

$$\tau = \frac{F}{2wl} \quad (1)$$

Where w , and l are the width and bonding length of the joint, respectively.

2.4 Contact angle and surface free energy measurements

The surface contact angles on the composites were measured with respect to the amount of embedded carbon black by the sessile drop method using a drop shape analysis system (DSA100, KRÜSS Germany). Distilled water, ethylene glycol and diiodomethane drops were deposited on the carbon black embedded composite. All the contact angles were measured within 10s after the probe liquids were deposited on the specimen in order to minimize the deviation in the measured contact angles.

The Lifshitz-van der Waals component of the surface free energy of a substance i is denoted by γ_i^{LW} [12]. Functionalization of the substance i introduces two additional components, γ_i^+ and γ_i^- , the acidic and basic components, respectively, which were represented by the acid-base component γ_i^{AB} of the surface free energy of the substance i as [12]:

$$\gamma_i^{AB} = 2\sqrt{\gamma_i^+ \gamma_i^-} \quad (2)$$

The total surface free energy γ_i of the substance i , is the sum of these components:

$$\gamma_i = \gamma_i^{LW} + \gamma_i^{AB} = \gamma_i^{LW} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_i^+ \gamma_i^-} \quad (3)$$

The relationship between the contact angles and the components of surface free energy is expressed by the vOCG (Oss-Chaudh Hury Good) equation [10]:

$$\gamma_L(1 + \cos\theta) = 2\sqrt{\gamma_S^{LW}\gamma_L^{LW}} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_S^+\gamma_L^-} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_S^-\gamma_L^+} \quad (4)$$

where subscripts L and S represent liquid adhesive and solid composite, respectively. Hence, it is possible to determine the three unknown components of the carbon black embedded composite γ_S^{LW} , γ_S^+ and γ_S^- if the contact angles are determined on the same surface with three different liquids (distilled water, diiodomethane and ethylene glycol). The surface free energies and their components for the probe liquids used in this study are listed in Table 4 [13].

2.5 AFM study

The surface characteristics of the glass/epoxy composite were measured with the AFM (XE-120, PSIA Inc., USA). The scan size was 1 μm x 1 μm . All the images had 256 data points with the scan rate of 1.0 Hz. From the AFM roughness analysis, the arithmetic surface roughness was calculated.

2.6 XPS study

XPS analysis was performed using an ESCALAB MK II spectrometer (VG Scientific, UK), which irradiated the surface of carbon black embedded composite with a monochromatic X-ray source (1253.6 eV), to determine the chemical binding states. The survey scans were recorded in the range 280-300 eV for the C_{1s} peaks.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 4 shows the SEM photograph of the composite surface on which the MEK was sprayed on the prepreg before curing. Since the MEK diluted the epoxy resin in the prepreg, the resin rich layer on the surface of cured composite became thinner and some bare fibers were exposed to the surface. The arithmetic surface roughness (R_a) of the composite increased as the sprayed amount of MEK was increased due to exposed fiber on the composite surface as shown in Fig. 5 (a). Fig. 5 (b) shows the lap shear strength of the composite adherend with respect to the amount of MEK. The maximum lap shear strength of the adhesive joint was 19.3 MPa, where the amount of MEK was 1.3 kg/m^2 . Then, the lap shear strength was almost constant when the amount of MEK was larger than 1.3 kg/m^2 , which was similar trend to the surface roughness. Fig. 6 shows the failure surface of the MEK treated composite adherend. When the amount of MEK was lower than 0.7 kg/m^2 , the interfacial failure occurred at the interface between the adhesive and the adherend. However, partial interfacial and partial cohesive failure modes occurred at the adhesive layer when the amount of MEK was larger than 1.3 kg/m^2 . From these results, it may be concluded that the thin epoxy layer and exposed fibers on the surface as shown in Fig. 4 (b) increased the lap shear strength of the composite adherend. Fig. 7 shows the stress-strain curve of the MEK treated composite with respect to the amount of MEK. The stiffness of the composite adherend slightly increased as the amount of MEK was increased, because the matrix content of composite adherend was reduced due to the dilution of epoxy resin of the prepreg. The tensile strength of the composite adherend was almost constant regardless of the amount of MEK, while the failure strain decreased slightly as the amount of MEK was increased.

Fig. 8 shows the SEM photographs on the surface of glass/epoxy embedded with CB (carbon black) particle. When the embedded amount of CB particle was 8.9 g/m^2 on

the surface of composite, some CB particles were exposed to the surface of epoxy resin. However, there was no difference in the surface roughness in micro scale compared to that of on the composite surface without embedment of CB particle as shown in Table 5. In order to observe the surface morphology in nano-scale of the CB particle embedded composite, the surfaces were measured with the AFM with respect to the amount of embedded CB particle as shown in Fig. 9. When the lass/epoxy composite was not embedded with CB particle, the surface was almost flat at arithmetic surface roughness (R_a) of 1.06 nm. The surface of CB particle embedded glass/epoxy composite became rougher as some CB particles were exposed on the surface. The arithmetic surface roughness in nano-scale of the composite increased as the amount of embedded CB particle was increased and the maximum surface roughness was 3.51 nm when the amount of embedded CB particle was 13.3 g/m² as shown in Fig. 10. Therefore, the protruded CB particles in the composite did not change the surface roughness in micro-scale, but changed roughness in nano-scale.

In order to observe the chemical characteristics of composite surface, the carbon bonds such as C–C, C–H, C–O and C=O of the composite surfaces were analyzed in order to investigate the chemical characteristics at the surface of CB particle embedded composite with the mathematical method recommended by Sherwood [14]. Each experimental C_{1s} spectrum at the surface of CB particle embedded composite was decomposed as shown in Fig. 11 by curve fitting using the binding energies of certain functional groups such as C–C, C–H, C–O and C=O listed in Table 6 [15]. Each carbon bond concentration on the composite surface was determined by the ratio of the area under the individual curves to the area under the original curve. Fig. 12 shows the carbon bond concentration ratios of C–O, C=O to C–C and C–H with respect to the amount of embedded CB particle. The chemical composition of composite surface without embedment included 74% C–C and C–H bonds and 26% C–O and C=O bonds. Both the C–O and C=O bonds on the composite surface increased as the amount of embedded CB particle was increased while the increment of the C–O bond was larger than that of the C=O bond. It was considered that the oxidized carbon layer on the surface of CB particle such as phenolic hydroxyl and carboxyl group increased C–O and C=O bonds on the composite surface [16].

Fig. 13 (a) shows the surface free energy of the CB particle embedded glass/epoxy composite. The surface free energy increased as the amount of embedded CB particle was increased because the surface roughness was increased when the contact angle on the composite was less than 90° , however the secondary force interactions due to oxidized carbon layer at the CB particle was increased between the liquid and composite surface [17]. Fig. 13 (b) shows the lap shear strength of the adhesive joint whose adherends were composed of the composite adherend with respect to the amount of embedded CB particle on the surface. The maximum lap shear strength was 17.4 MPa when the amount of embedded CB particle was 8.9 g/m². The lap shear strength of the joint increased as the amount of embedded CB particle was increased, where the interfacial failure at the bonding interface of the joint was changed into the partial interfacial and partial cohesive failures in the bonding layer of the joint as shown in Fig. 14. However, the lap shear strength decreased slightly when the amount of embedded CB particle was larger than 8.9 g/m², where the CB particle embedded layer in glass/epoxy composite locally was failed because the strength of the epoxy matrix decreased when the embedment of CB particle was too excessive as shown in Fig. 14 (d). Therefore, the lap shear strength of the adhesive joint could be increased when the

composite adherend was embedded with CB particle because CB increased the secondary force interaction as well as mechanical interlocking due to surface roughness in nano-scale between the adhesive and the composite adherend.

Fig. 15 shows the lap shear strengths of the adhesive joints when the epoxy matrix in the glass/epoxy composite adherend was diluted with MEK of 1.3 kg/m^2 and embedded with CB particle of 8.9 g/m^2 . The surface roughness of the CB particle embedded composite adherend was $1.91 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ due to the MEK treatment while the glass/epoxy composite adherends which were mechanically abraded with sand papers and grit blasted were $2.43 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $3.05 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, respectively. The lap shear strength of the adhesive joint whose adherends were CB particle surface-treated was 24.8 MPa , which is 5.5 times higher than that of the joint without surface treatment on the composite adherend. Also, it was even 40% higher than that of the joint with surface treatment of grit blast or mechanical abrasion. Therefore, it was concluded that CB particle embedded glass/composite adherend yielded good adhesion characteristics without requiring additional surface treatment.

4. Conclusion

In this study, the surfaces of glass/epoxy composites were embedded with carbon black and their adhesion characteristics were investigated with respect to the amount of embedment. From the investigation, the following conclusions were drawn.

The lap shear strength of the joint increased about 4 times without degrading the tensile strength of the composite, when the glass/epoxy composite prepreg was diluted with MEK of 1.3 kg/m^2 before curing process of the composite, which increased the surface roughness by the exposed fibers.

The lap shear strength of the joint increased about 3.5 times when the composite adherend was embedded with CB particle of 8.9 g/m^2 due to the increased surface roughness and surface free energy by the embedment.

The lap shear strength of the joint whose adherends were embedded with CB particle which were diluted in MEK increased about 40% compared to the composite adhesive joint whose adherends were grit blasted.

Fig 1. Fabrication procedure for the nano-particle embedded composites: (a) pre-mixing; (b) curing process of nano particle with the composite.

Fig 2. Tensile test specimen of glass/composite adherend of 3 mm thickness.

Fig 3. Adhesively bonded double lap joint with glass/composite adherend; (a) dimensions (mm); (b) photograph.

Fig 4. SEM micrographs of composite; (a) without MEK treatment; (b) treated with MEK of 1.3 kg/m²; (c) schematic diagram of the process of MEK treated composite.

Fig 5. Lap shear test results of the adhesive composite joint with respect to the amount of MEK: (a) surface roughness; (b) lap shear strength.

Fig 6. Photographs of failed composite surfaces of the adhesive joints with respect to the amount of MEK: (a) without treatment; (b) 0.2 kg/m²; (c) 1.3 kg/m²; (d) 1.8 kg/m².

Fig 7. Stress-strain curves of the glass/epoxy composite with respect to the amount of MEK.

Fig 8. SEM photographs of the surface of glass/epoxy composite: (a) without the embedment; (b) embedded with CB of 8.9 g/m²

Fig 9. AFM photographs at the surfaces of glass/epoxy composite with respect to amount of embedded CB: (a) 0 g/m²; (b) 1.3 g/m²; (c) 8.9 g/m²; (d) 13.3 g/m²

Fig 10. Arithmetic surface roughness of the epoxy adhesive composite joints with respect to the amount of embedded.

Fig 11. Deconvolution of C_{1s} spectra at the surfaces of composite with respect to amount of embedded: (a) 0 g/m^2 ; (b) 1.3 g/m^2 ; (c) 8.9 g/m^2 ; (d) 13.3 g/m^2

Fig 12. Carbon bond ratios of C-O, C=O to C-C and C-H at the surfaces of composite with respect to amount of embedded CB.

Fig 13. Lap shear test results of the epoxy adhesive composite joints with respect to the amount of embedded: (a) surface free energy; (b) lap shear strength.

Fig 14. Photographs of failed composite surfaces of the adhesive joints with respect to the amount of embedded CB: (a) 0 g/m^2 ; (b) 1.3 g/m^2 ; (c) 8.9 g/m^2 ; (d) 13.3 g/m^2

- 1: Without surface treatment
 2: Surface diluted with MEK of 1.3 kg/m² and embedded with CB of 8.9 g/m²
 3: Mechanically abraded with sand papers
 4: Grit blasted

Fig 15. Lap shear strengths of the epoxy adhesive composite adhesive joints with respect to the surface treatment method

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the glass/epoxy composite (UGN 200).

E_1 (GPa)	E_2, E_3 (GPa)	G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}, ν_{13}	ν_{23}	α_1 (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	α_2, α_3 (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)
37	8.6	3.8	1.86	0.28	0.4	7.0	21

E_1 : Modulus in the fiber direction

E_2, E_3 : Moduli in the transverse and thickness directions

G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23} : Shear moduli,

$\nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}$: Poisson's ratios

α_1 : CTE in the fiber direction,

α_2, α_3 : CTEs in the transverse and thickness directions

Table 2. Properties of the carbon black particle used.

Density	Nominal size	Shape
1800 kg/m ³	30 nm	Sphere

Table 3. Mechanical properties of the epoxy used.

Young's modulus	Poisson's ratio	Tensile strength
3.8 GPa	0.37	39 MPa

Table 4. Surface free energy components (mJ/m²) of the liquid [13]

	γ_L	γ_L^{LW}	γ_L^{AB}	γ_L^+	γ_L^-
Water	72.8	21.8	51.0	65.0	10.0
Ethylene glycol	48.0	31.4	16.4	1.58	42.5
Diiodomethane	50.8	50.8	0	0	0

Table 5. Arithmetic surface roughness (R_a) of the glass/epoxy composite with respect to the amount of embedded CB particle.

Amount of embedded CB (g/m ²)	0	1.3	2.0	8.9	13.3
Arithmetic surface roughness ($R_a, \mu\text{m}$)	0.53	0.55	0.50	0.58	0.51

Table 6. Binding energies of functional groups used for the decomposition of XPS C_{1s} peak [15]

Functional group	C-C, C-H	C-O	C=O
Binding energy (eV)	284.6 ± 0.1	286.2 ± 0.1	287.6 ± 0.1

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References

1. Lee D.G. and Suh N.P., in: *Axiomatic design and fabrication of composite structures, Application in robots, machine tools and automobiles*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, p. 14-61 (2006).
2. Hart-Smith L.J., In: Reinhart TJ, editors. in: *Composites*. Ohio: ASM International, p. 479-495 (1987).
3. Vinson J.R. and Sierakowski R.L., in: *The behavior of structures composed of composite materials.*, Dordrecht: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, (1987).
4. Niem P.I.F., Lau T.L. and Kwan K.M., "The effect of surface characteristics of polymeric materials on the strength of bonded joints," *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. 10 p. 361-372 (1996).
5. [5] Roizard X., Wery M. and Kirmann J., "Effects of alkaline etching on the surface roughness of a fibre-reinforced epoxy composite," *Composite structures*, Vol. 56, p. 223-228 (2002).
6. Kim J.K. and Lee D.G., "Adhesion Characteristics of Plasma Surface Treated Carbon Fiber - Epoxy Composite with respect to Release Films Used during Demolding," *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. 18, p. 473-494 (2004).
7. Benard Q., Fois M. and Grisel M., "Peel ply surface treatment for composite assemblies: Chemistry and morphology effects," *Composites- Part A*, Vol. 36, p. 1562-1568 (2005).
8. Chang L, Zhang Z, Breidt C, Friedrich ., "Tribological Properties of Epoxy Nanocomposites: I. Enhancement of the Wear Resistance By Nano-TiO₂ Particles," *Wear*, Vol. 258, p. 141-48 (2005).
9. Park S.W., Kim B.C. and Lee D.G., "Tensile Strength of Joints Bonded With a Nanoparticle Reinforced Adhesive" *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. 23, p. 95-113 (2009).
10. Van Oss C.J., Chaudhury M.K. and Good R.J., "Monopolar surfaces," *Advances in colloid and interface science*, Vol. 28, p. 35-64 (1987).
11. Choi, J.H. and Lee, D.G., "An Experimental Study of the Static Torque Capacity of the Adhesively-Bonded Tubular Single Lap Joint," *Journal of Adhesion*, Vol. 55, p. 245-260 (1996).
12. Good R.J., "Contact angle, wetting, and adhesion: a critical review," *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. 6, p. 1269-1302 (1992).
13. Della Volpe C. and Siboni S., "Some Reflections on Acid-Base Solid Surface Free Energy Theories," *J. Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, Vol. 195, p. 121-136 (1997).
14. Sherwood, P.M.A., "Data Analysis in XPS and AES," in: *Practical Surface Analysis*, Vol. 1, New York: John Wiley & Sons, Appendix 3 (1990).
15. Beamson, G. and Briggs, D., in: *High Resolution XPS of Organic Polymers- The Scienta ESCA 300 Database*, Chichester : John Willey & Sons (1992).
16. Donnet J.B., Bansal R.C., Wang M.J., in: *Carbon black - Science and Technology*, New York: Marcel Dekker, Inc., p. 177-215 (1993).
17. Kinloch, A.J., in: *Adhesion and Adhesives*, New York: Chapman & Hall, p. 23-24, 79-82 (1987).